

DEVELOPMENT OF ORAL SPEECH AND PRONUNCIATION IN CHILDREN

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Note: *This article discusses ways to develop oral speech in children, the causes and solutions of bad pronunciation.*

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Oral speech is widely used in social and working life, in everyday life. Due to the development of modern means of communication, such as telephone, television and the Internet, which allow the transmission of oral speech over long distances, the scope of its application is constantly expanding. Therefore, in institutions with children with hearing impairments, which are carried out in a specific way in the learning process, special attention is paid to the formation of oral speech to correct deficiencies along with the general development of first-graders, because speech mastery. their successful development is a necessary condition for their full integration into the hearing community.

Students with hearing impairments are identified before going to school:

pronunciation defects;

Limited vocabulary;

Inadequate mastery of the phonetic structure of words is manifested not only in incorrect pronunciation, but also in incorrect spelling of words;

Misunderstanding and misuse of words;

Disadvantages of the grammatical structure of the sentence: incorrect structure of the sentence, incorrect coordination within the sentence;

Limited comprehension of oral speech

As F.F. Raun argues that the quality of the phonetic design of a hearing-impaired person's speech determines how open he or she is to understanding others and to what extent it can be the basis for knowing a language.

The development, prospects, prosperity, spiritual growth of any country, its place among the most developed countries in the world depend on well-educated young people with high intellectual potential, noble qualities in heart and mind. It is the honorable and at the same time responsible duty of educators and educators to bring up a selfless, selfless generation that will serve the welfare of the people, to raise the content and quality of education to a higher level.

The organization of the development of a harmoniously developed person has always been an important requirement and the main goal of society. As a proof of this,

we can cite the words of our First President Islam Karimov: The National Training Program and the Education Law of August 29, 1997 are clear evidence of this. Accordingly, special attention is paid to teaching young people to express themselves independently and to understand the opinions of others. The Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis of January 24, 2020 pays special attention to the field of preschool education. According to him, it is necessary to introduce a system of preparing 6-year-olds for school and increase the coverage of children in preschool education by 60%. The content has been improved. , small poems. During this period, speech is formed not only as a means of communication with adults, but also with peers. It is during this period that the child's vocal pronunciation and listening skills develop. shake fast. The main task during this period is the continuous development of listening skills, strengthening and developing the organs of the speech apparatus. To achieve these goals, special sound groups are selected and children practice them based on sound imitation.

If 3-year-olds cannot pronounce sounds like s, z, sh, ch, r, l enough, they should not start practicing them right away, as these children may become accustomed to mispronouncing them.

Between the ages of 5 and 7, the formation of the correct pronunciation of sounds can be done in connection with the stratification of sounds that are often mixed by children. It is necessary to pay attention to the pronunciation of voiced and unvoiced sounds, v-f, z-s, j-sh, b-p, d-t, g-k and l, r.

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